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12 Nov 2021

RefSeq release 209 is now available online, from the FTP site and through NCBI's Entrez programming utilities. E-

A more modern PMC is on its way – there's still time to give us feedback!

08 Nov 2021

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07 Nov 2021

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2375-0605	AACE Clinical Case Reports	v.7(6) Nov-Dec 2021	v.5 2019	Immediate	Full
1550-7416	The AAPS Journal (v.1,1999)	v.18(3) May 2016	v.6 2004		No longer participating (Full)
1530-9932	AAPS PharmSciTech	v.17(2) Apr 2016	v.1 2000		No longer participating (Full)
2515-9321	AAS Open Research	v.8 2021	v.1 2018	Immediate	Full
1925-3621	Academic Forensic Pathology	v.11(2) Jun 2021	v.6 2016	12 months	Full
2374-2895	Academic Pathology	v.8 Jan-Dec 2021	v.1 2014	Immediate	Full
2516-8292	Access Microbiology	v.3(3) Mar 2021	v.1 2019	Immediate	Full
2326-3253	ACQ Case Reports Journal	v.8(11) Nov 2021	v.1 2013	Immediate	Full
2578-5745	AGR Open Rheumatology	v.3(10) Oct 2021	v.1 2019	Immediate	Full
2374-7943	ACS Central Science	v.7(10) Oct 27, 2021	v.1 2015	Immediate	Full
1948-7193	ACS Chemical Neuroscience	v.5(8) Aug 20, 2014	v.1 2010		No longer participating (Full)
1948-5875	ACS Medicinal Chemistry Letters	v.12(10) Oct 14, 2021	v.1 2010	12 months or less	Full
2470-1343	ACS Omega	v.6(43) Nov 2, 2021	v.1 2016	Immediate	Full
2575-9108	ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science	v.5(5) Oct 8, 2021	v.1 2018	12 months	Full
0392-4203	Acta Bio Medica - Atenei Parmensis	v.92(4) 2021	v.88 2017	Immediate	Full
1672-9145	Acta Biochimica et Biophysica Sinica	v.53(10) Oct 2021	v.41 2009	12 months	NIH Portfolio
1011-6842	Acta Caetologica Sinica	v.37(5) Sep 2021	v.29 2013	Immediate	Full
0102-8650	Acta Cirurgica Brasileira	v.36(2) 2021	v.34 2019	Immediate	Full
0353-9466	Acta Clinica Croatica	v.60(2) Jun 2021	v.57 2018	Immediate	Full
2052-5192	Acta Crystallographica Section B: Structural Science, Crystal Engineering and Materials	v.77(Pt 5) Oct 1, 2021	v.69 2013	12 months	NIH Portfolio
2056-9890	Acta Crystallographica Section E: Crystallographic Communications (v64,2008)	v.77(Pt 10) Oct 1, 2021	v.71 2015	Immediate	Full
2053-2733	Acta Crystallographica, Section A: Foundations and Advances	v.77(Pt 5) Sep 1, 2021	v.70 2014	12 months	NIH Portfolio
2053-2296	Acta Crystallographica, Section C: Structural Chemistry	v.77(Pt 10) Oct 1, 2021	v.70 2014	12 months	NIH Portfolio
2059-7983	Acta Crystallographica, Section D: Structural Biology	v.77(Pt 10) Oct 1, 2021	v.72 2016	12 months	NIH Portfolio
2053-230X	Acta Crystallographica, Section F: Structural Biology Communications (v61,2005)	v.77(Pt 10) Oct 1, 2021	v.70 2014	12 months or less	Full
0001-5547	Acta Cytologica	v.55(8) Dec 2011	v.55 2011		No longer participating (NIHP)
1841-0987	Acta Endocrinologica (Bucharest)	v.17(1) Apr-Jun 2021	v.12 2016	6 months	Full
0001-5792	Acta Haematologica	v.127(3) Mar 2012	v.121 2009		No longer participating (NIHP)
0044-5993	Acta Histochemica et Cytochemica	v.54(5) Oct 29, 2021	v.39 2006	Immediate	Full
0353-8109	Acta Informatica Medica	v.29(2) Sep 2021	v.16 2008	Immediate	Full
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1128-2460	Acta Myologica	v.60(2) Sep 2021	v.26 2007	Immediate	Full
2075-8251	Acta Naturae	v.13(3) Jul-Sep 2021	v.1 2009	Immediate	Full
2051-5960	Acta Neuroethologica Communications	v.9 2021	v.1 2013	Immediate	Full
1745-3674	Acta Orthopaedica	v.92(5) 2021	v.80 2009	Immediate	Full
1017-995X	Acta Orthopaedica et Traumatologica Turcica	v.55(1) Apr 2021	v.50 2016	Immediate	Full
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0392-100X	Acta Otorinolaryngologica Italica	v.51(4) Aug 2021	v.25 2005	Immediate	Full
2211-3835	Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica, B	v.11(10) v.11(11)	v.4 v.5	Immediate	Full

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	v.4(5) Oct 8, 2021	v.1 2018	12 months	Full
	v.92(4) 2021	v.88 2017	Immediate	Full
	v.53(10) Oct 2021	v.41 2009	12 months	NIH Portfolio
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	v.77(Pt 10) Oct 1, 2021	v.70 2014	12 months or less	...

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0510-8659	Bulletin of the World Health Organization, Supplement	v.7 1953
2321-3868	Burns & Trauma	v.9 2021

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1. [Rajeev Chawla, S. V. Madhu, B. M. Makkar, Sujoy Ghosh, Banshi Saboo, Sarjay Kalra, On behalf of the RSSDI-ESI Consensus Group](#)
Indian J Endocrinol Metab. 2020 Jan-Feb; 24(1): 1-122. doi: 10.4103/ijem.IJEM_225_20
Correction in: *Indian J Endocrinol Metab.* 2020 Jul-Aug; 24(4): 376.
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- [Resveratrol provides benefits in mice with type II diabetes-induced chronic renal failure through AMPK signaling pathway](#)
2. [Haiyan Guo, Linyun Zhang](#)
Exp Ther Med. 2018 Jul; 16(1): 333-341. Published online 2018 May 17. doi: 10.3892/etm.2018.6178
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- [Age, sex, disease severity, and disease duration difference in placebo response: implications from a meta-analysis of diabetes mellitus](#)
3. [Chu Lin, Xiaoling Cai, Wenjia Yang, Fang Lv, Lin Nie, Limong Ji](#)
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4. [Shuhua Tian, Xiangfei Li, Yunfan Wang, Yingjian Lu](#)
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